

Eurodoc Statement on the 20th Anniversary of the Salzburg Recommendations

Doctoral education today, tomorrow, and 20 years from now

This year, the Salzburg Recommendations celebrate their 20-year anniversary. Since 2005, they have set the **gold standard for European doctoral education**. **The Salzburg Recommendations have paved the way for increased institutional responsibility** for doctoral education and have enhanced the quality of doctoral education across Europe.

The current alignment of doctoral education across Europe is a direct outcome of the Bologna process, the establishment of the European Higher Education Area (EHEA), and the establishment of the European Research Area (ERA). This alignment has enabled European mobility of researchers, enhanced European competitiveness, and contributed to developing the European Dimension in academia.

A 20-year anniversary calls for revisiting the principles and reflecting on how they can remain as fit for purpose as they were in 2005 and 2010. This conversation should involve everyone in the academic community. With this publication, Eurodoc – representing doctoral candidates, postdoctoral and other early career researchers across Europe – highlights key **successes**, delineates the **remaining implementation gaps**, and concludes with **recommendations** for an update of the Salzburg Recommendations.

The Salzburg Recommendations: A success story for European doctoral training

The Salzburg Recommendations have aged well. There is no doubt that the Salzburg Recommendations have been incredibly successful in transforming European doctoral training. **The most important aspects of the recommendations are the recognition that doctoral candidates are professionals, that doctoral education plays a central role in shaping the future of higher education, and that quality in doctoral education is intimately linked to impactful research and innovation.** The European higher education landscape is diverse and this diversity is one of its strengths. The Salzburg Recommendations are adapted to this diversity by providing strategic recommendations on key areas of alignment, while leaving appropriate space for institutional practices and regional context.

Doctoral education is the meeting-point of higher education and research in Europe: This is where the future of academia is shaped. With their emphasis on doctoral education as a research education, on the institutional responsibility for it, and on doctoral candidates being early stage research professionals, the recommendations have been a **major driving force to increase the quality of doctoral education across Europe**. The focus on transferable skills as well as on intersectorial, interfield, and international mobility have enhanced the value of the PhD across sectors and underlined the importance of research within and outside of higher education.

High quality doctoral education is achieved when candidates are embedded in thriving and stimulating research environments. The role of institutions is to enable research enthusiasm, curiosity, and creativity. **Institutions must recognise their responsibility for high-quality supervision and the doctoral candidates' right to mentorship.**

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Implementation gaps from the Salzburg Recommendations

However, 20 years in, there remain implementation gaps that need to be addressed: Today, like 20 years ago, we still need to reiterate that the work of doctoral candidates has to be fully recognised by academia – and society at large.

The **persistent lack of sustainable funding** for doctoral education remains one of the largest obstacles to quality doctoral education. Funding for research and research education in Europe today is fragmented and short-term, creating precarious conditions for those working in the higher education and research sector. The Salzburg Recommendations state that doctoral candidates are professionals. Yet this is not reflected in how doctoral candidates are in reality financially compensated.¹ **Financial compensation of doctoral candidates must reflect the time commitment and qualifications required of them as research professionals.** Failure to compensate doctoral candidates financially is an example of the underfunding of the higher education and research sector.

The Salzburg Recommendations have furthermore proven too vague on the recommended duration of doctoral education. While they state that doctoral education is **assumed to be 3-4 years full-time**, it remains necessary to emphasize that this only applies when the **majority of this time is spent on research** and only **secondarily spent on course work of doctoral candidates**. Other duties such as teaching and administrative tasks for their institution have to result in respective adequate prolongation and compensation.

By highlighting the need for critical mass, the Salzburg Recommendations have aimed to ensure that doctoral candidates are embedded in a lively research environment consisting of both peers and senior colleagues. The implementation of doctoral schools has been a means for achieving this – to some degree. Doctoral schools, as experience has shown, also come with the risk of overregulation. **It is important that the individual remains at the heart of doctoral education.** This entails that doctoral candidates can shape their coursework as well their research, even when it is part of collaborative research projects.

Though the Salzburg II recommendations specifically address quality assurance of doctoral education, there is still, unfortunately, **a long way to go for quality assurance of doctoral education to be coherently implemented across Europe.** Whereas research assessment can serve as a proxy for whether researchers, including doctoral candidates, are embedded into thriving research environments, it does not serve as a proxy for whether the frameworks of doctoral education support their development of expert and transferable skills. Quality assurance of doctoral education differs from quality assurance of the research conducted by doctoral candidates, their supervisors, or other researchers within their institutions. Importantly, quality assurance should address whether the framework conditions provided for doctoral candidates and doctoral education are aligned or misaligned with the Salzburg recommendations.

¹ Eurodoc distinguishes between cases where doctoral candidates are carrying out their doctoral education part time and receive financial compensation accordingly, and the practice of employing doctoral candidates on part-time contracts with the expectation that they work (more than) full time. While the first ensures non-linear possibilities for completing a PhD, the latter is yet another symptom that shows how underfunded doctoral education and research and higher education is.

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The Salzburg Recommendations: A vision for tomorrow

When the Salzburg Recommendations were first written, and then updated, it was necessary to emphasise the role of doctoral education for society at large and to stress the importance of researchers in non-academic careers. **What is missing is a clear statement on the role of doctoral education for the higher education system itself.** For academia, today's doctoral candidates are tomorrow's professors and academic leaders. The Salzburg Recommendations should

- **emphasise the importance of doctoral education** as key for how **higher education shapes its own future.**

Thus, it is crucial that academic institutions have **freedom to decide on the existence and content of doctoral schools and programmes** to ensure their **institutional autonomy.**

In addition, what should be included in the Salzburg Recommendations fit for the future are the following three foundations:

- the importance of ensuring **academic integrity** and nurturing **public trust**
- the **EHEA fundamental values**
- the **social dimension** of higher education

And last but not least, the importance of **nurturing public trust also needs to be taken up.** While transparent frameworks and quality assurance is mentioned in the Salzburg Recommendations, their implementation is, unfortunately, **in many cases still lacking.** It should be explicitly mentioned that **quality assurance** needs to focus on the frameworks in place for doctoral education. These frameworks need to

- balance the rights and responsibilities of doctoral candidates, their supervisors, and the institution itself in such a way that **doctoral candidates have reasonable influence on their research and coursework** – even when part of a collaborative project.
- ensure that doctoral candidates are **guaranteed quality supervision** and that supervisors are trained and have enough working hours in their work plan allocated to supervisory tasks.
- ensure the right of doctoral candidates to **examination and to fair and transparent assessment processes.**

To ensure integrity and public trust in research, furthermore, the research of doctoral candidates needs to be assessed against its field-specific standards in transparent ways and aligned with Open Science practices.

- All assessment of doctoral candidates – whether of their research, their coursework, or other educational activities – must be subject to **fair and transparent processes.**
- **As doctoral education is a research education,** the examination of doctoral education means an assessment of the research performed during doctoral training. This assessment and assessment criteria should be **public and transparent.** The

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final assessment of the research conducted by the doctoral candidate is an act of research assessment and must be done by the research community alone, but crucially in a public and transparent manner such as to ensure **standards of quality, as well as the integrity and trustworthiness of the process.**

Doctoral candidates must be provided with opportunities and quality training to prepare themselves for the role as members of the academic community within academia as well as in society. The promotion and protection of the fundamental values of EHEA should be put at the core of academia, which means it has to become a central part of doctoral education.

- Doctoral education must equip candidates to uphold the democratic mission of European higher education. Thus, the **fundamental values of EHEA must be embedded into doctoral education** just as transferable skills have come to be understood as a core part of high quality doctoral training. Training in academic freedom, research integrity, and active participation in academic governance at all levels must be put at the core of the Salzburg Recommendations.

Over the years, a strong focus in the Bologna process on **equitable opportunities and the social dimension of higher education** has emerged, which we would like to see reflected in the Salzburg Recommendations. The precarity of research careers comes with a higher cost to those from underrepresented and marginalised groups such as women, first generation academics, or third country nationals.

- Doctoral education must also fulfill the **social dimension of the mission of higher education**. Systemic barriers faced by underrepresented groups in the higher education and research sector must be addressed and mitigated, to ensure that pursuing a research career is attractive to all with the talent disregarding their background.

The social dimension also extends to the creation of an inclusive and supportive work environment for doctoral candidates. The academic workforce, at all career stages, reports problematic levels of poor mental health as compared to other sectors.

- Institutional responsibility must include providing doctoral candidates as well as their supervisors with a **healthy work environment** (including the necessary support to prevent mental health issues) and **sustainable working conditions** (such as manageable workloads, more stable career paths). This includes reasonable ratios between permanent and precariously employed academic staff, as well as reasonable ratios between staff and students.
- Ensuring the social dimension of higher education is implemented in doctoral education accordingly necessitates **sufficient and sustainable funding that lives up to the targets of EHEA and ERA in regard to the public spending on the sector.**

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About this document

This document was prepared by Pil Maria Saugmann, Karl Kilbo Edlund, and Hannah Schoch based on discussions from the administrative board of Eurodoc, members of the secretariat of Eurodoc, representatives of early career researchers from across Europe and delegates of Eurodoc's National Member Organisations.

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Eurodoc, the European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers, is a grassroots federation of 26 national associations of early career researchers (ECRs) from 26 countries across Europe. Eurodoc was established in 2002 and is based in Brussels. As a representative of doctoral candidates and junior researchers at the European level, Eurodoc engages with all major stakeholders in research, higher education, and innovation in Europe.

